

**DIRECTIONS FOR EFFECTIVE PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN'S TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES****Muydinova Gulnozakhon Kahramon kizi**

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The textile industry occupies one of the most important positions in the world's economy and is considered one of the key sectors producing consumer goods, which are essential to the market, such as clothing, fabrics, and knitwear products.

Uzbekistan possesses a rich raw material base (cotton, wool, karakul, oil, gas, and other raw materials) necessary for the development of all sectors of the textile industry and the rapid economic growth. The country also has favorable natural-climatic, territorial, and labor resources required for this development. The textile industry in our Republic is advancing at a fast pace. While only 7% of the cotton fiber produced in our Republic was processed in 1991, today, 100% of the cotton raw material is being processed by textile industry enterprises.

For the further development of the sector, the Development Program for 2022-2026 plans to implement 225 new projects with a total value of 2.437 billion USD, aimed at creating 80,000 new jobs. The share of the textile industry in the country's total industrial production increased from 5.2% in 2016 to 7.3% in 2022 [4]. By 2023, the volume of textile production had grown 4.7 times compared to 2017, indicating its rapid development relative to other sectors of the economy [1].

In 2017, the number of industrial enterprises specializing in light industry, particularly in textile production, significantly increased within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, the pandemic in 2019 and the geopolitical changes in the world in 2022 negatively impacted the economies of countries, including enterprises in the textile industry.

On the other hand, considering that the textile industry is a labor-intensive sector, over 450,000 people are employed in this industry nationwide, with 80% of them being women. The implementation of new projects has led to a continuous increase in these figures. In 2023, the establishment of 86 textile enterprises resulted in over 23,000 people being provided with permanent jobs. Additionally, research has revealed that there are over 35,000 vacancies in textile industry enterprises, with this number continuing to grow daily. The development of this sector plays a crucial role in ensuring employment, improving living standards, and enhancing the well-being of the population.

Based on the research into the innovative development of Uzbekistan's textile industry, the following conclusions can be drawn regarding the main problems of the strategic development of the industry:

- Imperfections in Legislation. The existing legislation in the consumer goods market is inadequate and needs improvement.
- Lack of Highly Qualified Specialists. There is a shortage of skilled professionals in the industry.
- Low Level of Investment and Innovation. The industry experiences a low level of investment and innovative activities.

Addressing these issues should be directed towards the advancement of modern technologies, which will enable:

- Increased Economic Growth. Accelerate the rate of economic growth in the industry.
- Higher Domestic Product Share. Enhance the proportion of domestic products within the internal market.
- Improved Profitability. Raise the profitability of produced goods and services.
- Provision of Highly Qualified Specialists. Ensure the textile industry is supported by highly skilled professionals.

Currently, a unique Uzbek-South Korean project is being implemented, unparalleled in the entire CIS region [2]. This represents the future of Uzbekistan's textile industry—the educational and research textile technopark. This facility will train personnel for textile enterprises of a new generation, equipped not only with modern machinery but also utilizing the latest information and communication technologies.

As a result of ongoing reforms in the Republic, significant positive outcomes have been achieved in the production of industrial goods and ensuring their competitiveness. To further enhance product competitiveness and implement safe development in industrial enterprises, it is essential to develop and define comprehensive, well-founded measures, key directions, and economic development concepts for the future. This will be crucial for achieving success in the sector.

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